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Defending the Dark Arts: The Construction of the Witch figure in Greek and Japanese Mythologies through Circe in “The Odyssey” and Yubaba in *Spirited Away*

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Abstract:

Witches have been claimed to have existed since the very dawn of humankind. One of their earliest appearances in written records was in the Bible, Book I of Samuel, where King Saul sought her out to summon Samuel’s spirit in order to help him defeat the Philistine army. The witch had complied, yet the Old Testament goes on to condemn witches. Many women persecuted during the almost three centuries of illogical witch hunting were simply women living alone or were the wise women of their villages. This leads to the inevitable topic of discussion – the figure of an independent woman in a patriarchal world. As Laura Mulvey states, the idea of a woman is central to the patriarchal system. It is her lack that produces the phallus as a symbolic presence, it is her desire to make good the lack that the phallus signifies. A single woman without that desire would seem to appear as a threat. Thus, this paper aims to analyze the portrayal of witches through that of Circe – owing a lot of her popularity to the tenth book of “The Odyssey”, a lone woman on an isolated island; and Yubaba, Circe’s Studio Ghibli representation, as instances of stereotypical witches and the feminist implications of the same. While Japanese mythology has many spirits that correspond to Yubaba, the very obvious reference to Circe turning unwanted people invading

her territory into pigs cannot be overlooked. Depictions of witches in contemporary times continue to show them as the wicked old ladies – with no regard to their background, the events that brought them to such a pass. Historical and mythological analyses and an in-depth study of women through the ages, witches, and the focused characters will be undertaken in this paper to reveal that the actions of these women were only ever seen superficially – leading to them being wrongly villainized.

Keywords: Witches, Patriarchal system, Mythology, Folklore, Mothers, Paternity anxiety.

Introduction

The bulk of Circe’s image in front of humankind has been crafted by her appearance in the tenth book of the Homeric epic, *The Odyssey*. It chronicles the journey of Odysseus back to Ithaca, his home, after the Trojan War. He has been cursed by Poseidon to twenty years of wandering and stumbles upon the island of Circe. Hesoid’s *Theogony* places Circe in the massive family tree of Greek Gods and Goddesses as the daughter of the Titan God of the Sun, Helios and the Ocean nymph Perses. Her siblings consisted of Pasiphae, the mother of the Minotaur; Aetes, the King of Colchos and the Keeper of the Golden fleece; and Perses, namesake to his mother, and the least well known among the children of Helios. While no ancient sources exist to establish why Circe lives on the island of Aea, Madeline Miller’s book offers a possible suggestion – she admitted to practising witchcraft. This made her and her siblings extraordinary, even in a star-studded court of powerful gods and titans. They were of a kind that had not existed before, and hence a threat to the status quo of the Greek godships. Written by the Greek historian Diodorus Siculus, *The Library of History* lays out Aetes and Perses as the only children of Helios and Hecate, the daughter of Perses. She

poisons her father and marries her uncle, Aeetes, giving birth to their daughters, Circe and Medea. Circe, in this narrative, poisons her husband and is hence deposed from her throne. She then flees to Oceanus and seizes an island for herself. In the most commonly accepted strand of mythology, however, there is no evidence of her being exiled. In *The Odyssey*, Odysseus narrates her as being attended by nereids. Thus, she is not entirely alone either.

Yubaba, the witch of *Spirited Away*, probably draws her name from the term *yamauba* or *yamanba* or *yamamba*, all of which are used interchangeably. The term *uba* means “an ordinary old woman”. Yamaoka Genrin (1631-1672) believed this *uba* was more akin to the *hime* of *Tatsutahime* (goddess of autumn); thus, broadening its horizons to liken Folklorist Yanagita Kunio’s view that *yamauba* and *yamahime* were euphemisms for a mysterious woman living in the forest. has her roots in two prominent figures in Japanese folklore – the *Yokai* and the *Oni*. Folklorist Konno Ensuke opined that *yokai*-like creatures that lived in the mountains were called *yamauba* if they were old. Yanagita speculated that *yokai* were the deities that had fallen from grace. They were not worshipped anymore. According to Ema Tsutomu, author of *Nihon yokai shapeshifters*, the *yokai* found in folk tales before the Muromachi period (1336-1573) took mostly male forms. Before the first appearance of the term *Yamauba* in the Muromachi period, the witches of the mountains were addressed as *oni*. *Yokai* with strong negative association were known as *oni*. An *oni* is a demon depicted with a masculine body, wearing only a tiger-skin loincloth. It also usually has horns and sometimes a third eye in the centre of its forehead. They have no fixed gender and can manifest themselves as male or female (Copeland 20). The *oni* woman is often associated with cannibalism. In the sixth episode of *Ise monogatari*, a couple elope together and take shelter in a storehouse at night during a thunderstorm. The man stands guard at the entrance, but the woman is devoured by an *oni*. The *oni* could apparently also change into a handsome man to lure women. The *oni* woman is characterized, first and foremost, by rage. The *yamauba* can

be differentiated from the *oni* in tales where both of them appear, in the *Ubakawa* (The Old Woman Skin) type stories. In these, a stepmother drives the stepdaughter away, who finds a lonely house in the mountains with a lone old woman in it. The old woman warns her that it is an *oni*'s house and gives her an *ubakawa*, which makes her appear ugly and old. She is then employed in a rich man's house whose son catches a glimpse of her in her true form and falls in love. A kind of test is performed to identify her, and she marries the son to live happily ever after. Thus, *yamauba*, as a mountain deity, has both negative and positive connotations attached to her – like the two sides of a coin. Yubaba, in the movie, *Spirited Away*, similarly captures Haku, sends him on dangerous errands, and does not care about him when he is fatally injured. If this part of Yubaba is the *oni* woman, the *yamauba* part of her has two representations. The first is in the form of the mistress of the bath house that employed many in the spiritual world, and the second is in the form of Zeniba, her twin sister. Zeniba is the complete opposite of Yubaba – living as a recluse in a place where the train does not go back from and shows no greed for anything that she could procure by her magic, that the world outside offers. She gives Chihiro, the protagonist, important advice and forgives Haku for stealing her seal on the orders of Yubaba.

Why Witches Were Women

The image of the old woman stirring her cauldron, uttering incantations, drawing children to her house like in Hansel and Gretel, Rapunzel has been integrated into children's minds through fairytales, and as Disney movies and their live-action remakes continue to score blockbusters, witches remain at their core, though often unsung. Edward Dutton sets “group selection” as a reason for the persecution of witches in eighteenth-century Europe. It was explained as groups rivaling each other for survival in the harsh pre-industrial conditions, a derivation of Darwinian Theory. Dutton further brings in religion, “Religion, we will see, was trying to ensure that its adherents were optimally adapted to the conditions they faced, such

that they were successful in procreating. It did this, as all surviving groups have done, by identifying adaptive behavior and prescribing that behavior as the will of God, such that it was even more likely to be pursued.” Acute religiousness often accompanies phases of Darwinian struggles, allowing people to think their lives had meaning. The end of the Medieval Warm period brought on a cold period around 1350 and the Black Death added to the devastation and paralleled a rise in the persecution of witches, so did the Civil War in England that ended in 1649. British Canadian psychologist J.Philippe Rushton formulated his “Genetic Similarity Theory” – the idea that people act to maximize their indirect genetic interests, leading to group selection. Cooperative groups were more likely to survive longer. If males were assured that they were not being cuckolded, it reduced paternity anxiety and inter-male conflict. Thus, a patriarchal system also became the will of God. Witches were therefore women who were seen as likely to upset this equilibrium – widowed and unmarried women. Women in solitude, without a male cohort, were seen as dangerous and hence such that should not be allowed to exist. Several women persecuted were also marked as ‘unattractive’ or those with ‘Witch’s marks’, some prominent disfigurement.

Ancient Greeks have been known to accept physiognomy, the ancient art of judging a person’s psychology from their physical looks. Aristotle wrote in *Prior Analytics*, “It is possible to infer character from features.” Circe in Madeline Miller’s work is described as, “Her hair is streaked like a lynx. And her chin. There is a sharpness to it that is less than pleasing”. Her yellow eyes that proved her lineage as the daughter of the Sun have been emphasized by Homer. However, she was named Circe, meaning ‘Hawk’, because of them. Her siblings were considered more attractive. Scylla, a nymph won the heart of Glaucos with her beauty, not Circe who had been love with him. Her jealousy was the incentive that led to her mixing her herbs in the little pool that Scylla loved. Ovid describes the monster that Circe created, as “seeking her thighs, her legs, her feet, in place of them finds jaws like Cereberus”

(translated by Kline). Evans-Pritchard uses the term ‘spiteful.’ A woman could get herself accused of witchcraft simply by ‘cursing’ someone due to the nocebo effect. Between 1560 and 1600, some eight thousand elderly women were burned as witches in Scotland. Approximately 85 percent of those in England between 1566-1666 were women older than fifty, roughly 40 percent were widows and the rest had never married. Many of them were of low socio-economic status. David Pickering opined that witch hunters showed a “marked preference for elderly, ignorant women who lived as outcasts from the local community” and also, “Anyone with a squint, with eyebrows joined in the middle, or with a generally unattractive physical appearance.” In Carinthia in Austria, beggars were accused of being witches to quell the guilt from not being able to help them thus, resulting in a large number of male ‘witches’ being persecuted in the region. John Swain summarizes, “Witches were often poor old women who were usually accused by more prosperous younger neighbours, following a refusal of charity.” In the seventeenth century, begging had been banned, and replaced by the Poor Law. This meant that people had to pay tax to support paupers and paupers effectively became the parasites of the community. Those accused of witchcraft were, thus already a drain on society. Circe’s origin story does not narrate where she lived till she left for Aea. Rejected in love twice, she does not get a demigod to marry like her sister Pasiphae or a kingdom to rule like her brothers. Her residence in the house of Helios would be a drain on her father’s resources, except the riches of the Titans, like the Olympian Gods, were seemingly unfathomable. Her final fate being entwined with Telemachus, the son of her lover, Odysseus, does not bode well for her image either. *The Odyssey*, however, also tells of Penelope marrying Circe’s son, Telegonos. The epics are rife with Zeus’ escapades, and in the “Orphic Hymn 30”, Zeus is said to have slept with his daughter, Persephone, to give birth to Zagreos who later becomes Dionysus. His image as the God of the Olympians has remained untarnished.

In *Malleus Maleficarum* by Heinrich Kramer and James Sprenger, witches were those who, “voluntarily prostitute themselves to Incubus devils”. Dutton argues that prostitution thus undermined the patriarchy as it meant women sleeping with more than one man and earning money independently. Prostitution became socially unacceptable at around the same time as witchcraft, around the fifteenth century. Circe has fallen in love multiple times- with Glaucus, and once again, in a similar way to Picus, the son of Saturn in Roman mythology. Picus however, remains faithful to his wife, the nymph Canens and Circe turns him into a woodpecker (Ovid, Book XV). In Miller’s book, she also sleeps with Daedalus and has a relationship with Hermes, the God of Travellers and thieves. In the *Odyssey*, Odysseus and Circe make love despite Odysseus’ reminiscence about his wife Penelope and the child Telemachus that he had left behind. Circe thus became a symbol of a predatory woman, sexually independent and notorious for turning men into animals, subverting the patriarchal status quo. Ovid’s *Metamorphoses* describes the moment of Ulysses seeing Circe for the first time as her sitting, “...on her sacred throne, wearing a shining robe, covered over with a gold-embroidered veil. Nereids and nymphs were with her...”.

Rachel Grant and Tamara Montrose have formed the Life History Strategy model that takes into account physical and mental traits in an ecology where one has to respond to sudden unpredictable challenges. People who follow a fast LHS are r-strategists and live for the ‘now’. The K-strategists are the kind to “live slow and die old”. Husbands were extreme r-strategists, the males existing only to pass on their genes, and patriarchy ensured this. An objection to this model was the explanation that witches were simply irritable old women that their neighbours wanted to get rid of. While this might have been a reason, it also leaves out why unpleasant old men were not given the same fate.

Circe’s skills in transfiguration are perhaps the most known through the *Odyssey*. She transformed Odysseus’ men into pigs – what she thought was their true form because of the

way they were behaving in her residence. Greed is what turned them into pigs according to the legends; Miller however, provides an alternative reason. She was raped by human sailors who chanced upon her island – unable to resist when they learnt that there was no man in the house. In a poignant narration, Circe looks up to the sky, the sun, where her father, Helios keeps vigil but he does not arrive in his Titan form to protect his daughter, a Titaness. Thus, Circe takes pre-emptive measures every time from then on when a human ship anchors at her island. While a mythological basis is lacking for Miller’s version, there are enough examples throughout history about conquerors and their armies who defeated kingdoms and then looted, plundered and raped their women.

“...the males who passed on their genes to the greatest extent would have defeated other tribes in war and would have forcefully dominated their women. In other words, males who violently took what they wanted dominated the gene pool, including impregnating women whether the women were willing or not” (Dutton 221).

This also ties back to the group selection theory.

Yubaba is seen to be adept in transfiguration – she can transform herself, something that Circe was limited in, being only able to create illusions. She can turn into a bird, and flies across the expanse of her kingdom to look for Chihiro, the human intruder in her carefully created order. Her magic also turns Chihiro’s parents into pigs – again, a symbol of their unfettered greed as soon as they see the food in front. She is a prime example of the type of woman that would be persecuted as a witch in the European context, physically unattractive, old and ‘spiteful’. A *yamauba* is often translated to a ‘mountain witch’. She is often described as tall, with long hair, piercing eyes, and a large mouth that opens from ear to ear (Komatsu 2000, 428). *Yamauba*’s residence in the mountains also has significance. A scholar of religious studies, Miyake Hitoshi wrote, “Mountains are viewed as the dwelling place of the

dead and ancestor spirits” and “Mountains are regarded as liminal space between this world and the otherworld.” The entrance to Yubaba’s spiritual world is through an abandoned railway tunnel, which can also be a demarcation point between one world and the other, a bridge between the two. The residence of the *yamauba*, the mountains, is the realm where the *oni* and the *yokai* live with other deities and ancestors. Yubaba’s bath house is also where all supernatural beings merge to unwind (Reider 14). She also lives high above the flat ground, on the top floor of her bath house.

The most well-known story about the negative *yamauba* is that of *Kuwazu nyobo* (‘The Wife Who Does Not Eat’). It is about a man who wants a wife who does not eat. Soon, a beautiful woman who supposedly does not eat appears at his house. They get married but what he does not know is that she is a monster with a second mouth behind her head, with which she eats ravenously while the husband is not at home. Reider writes that according to the tales, when he discovers, the *yamauba* shows her true form, and the husband throws mugwort and iris at her to kill her. While the folktale intends to be didactic, Fujishiro Yumiko connects the *yamauba* in the tale to those women who are perfect in front of their husbands but have eating disorders, especially bulimia nervosa (2015, 55-63). Yamaguchi Motoko finds a similar connection to patients of anorexia nervosa, the fear of gaining weight (2009, 85-88). Japanese women, especially, are under the pressure to be pleasant, and a big appetite is frowned upon.

“The delineation of these ravenous figures suggests an overwhelming preoccupation with the danger posed by female consumption as well as the need to defuse the threat, leading us to question whether the provenance of such man-eaters, ironically, is rather in the realm of male anxieties about castration than simply in female notions of resistance.” (Vishwanathan 242-243)

Circe turning Odysseus’ crew into pigs as they gorged on her food was one of the few times that men in myth were punished for their appetites, and it is “the work of an unnatural woman” (Zimmerman 45). Right next to the monster that she created was Charybdis, described as a voracious monster. She swallows everything in her way, representing, as anthropologist David Gilmore says, “an archetypal image: that of losing control”. She is a cautionary tale, not to Odysseus’ sailors, but to women, “Hunger destroys control” (Zimmerman 46). The Muromachi period, when the term *yamauba* came to exist, was known as the early modern period and was a dark age for Japanese women (*Hayashi*); their social activities were limited, and delivery of dowries became common. “...a new term for divorce (*oidasu*, to chase out [the wife]). Moreover, the wife increasingly came to be viewed as the husband’s possession” (Farris 156).

Komatsu Kazuhiko who studies the *yamauba* in the village of Monobe, in Kochi prefecture wrote that the people believed in *yamauba* because it played certain societal roles, one of them being to explain the cause of madness and diseases in old women. The Japanese society is known for its overwhelming aged population thus; dementia is familiar to the people of contemporary people. In 1947, the average life expectancy for men and women was fifty and fifty-four respectively (*Tokudome et al*), and it is easy to imagine that in centuries prior elderly people would be rare, and afflictions common to elderly people even rarer. Dementia and strokes were often attributed to the *yamauba*’s role. Yanagita Kunio, noting the large number of people with dementia that went missing in 2018 itself, opines that a lot of the old mountain witches were women who had wandered off in the later stages of dementia. The issue of *yamauba* having an enormous appetite could be a sign of memories of famines in villages. It could also be a sign of frontotemporal dementia (FTD), symptoms of which include increasingly inappropriate actions, lack of judgment and inhibition, and overeating (Mayo Clinic n.d.). Respect for elders is encouraged in Confucian philosophy and

most elderly people in Japan live happily surrounded by their family. However, the *yamauba* in *Hanayo no hime* outlived all her children, and none of her grandchildren would take her in. She was forced to live by herself and went off to the mountains. Hers is the story of *Obasute-yama*, an abandoned woman in the mountains. Edward Drott writes, “On the one hand auditors were often encouraged to empathize with elders and reflect on the fact that all will encounter such miseries should they live long enough. On the other hand, certain works presented the aged body as an unsettling other, to inspire fear or disgust and encourage the faithful to engage in practices that could rescue them from attachment to the human form....” In most *noh* plays, old women are seen as the symbol of shame. However, in plays such as *Koi no omoni* (Heavy load of love) and *Aya no tsuzumi* (Damask drum), old men fall in love with beautiful ladies but their appearances are not described in a shameful manner (Reider 177).

Mothers and Hosts

Circe turns people into pigs but she is also a very gracious host. In Apollonius Rhodius’ *Argonautica*, Jason and Medea arrive at the island of Circe, having stolen the Golden Fleece from Colchos, Aeetes’ domain. Their flight is stopped by the Colchians who defended their possession but it led to the death of Apsyrtus, Medea’s brother. They arrived at Circe’s Island to be purified of *chiasma* or sin. This forms an ironic scene; the person performing the purifying ritual is the aunt of the victim of the sin. When Medea delivers her speech, she recounts the Argonauts’ struggles before coming to her own precarious position. Her purpose is to try and soften Circe’s wrath that may emerge when she comes to know the true state of events. Medea’s subordinate position towards Circe is reflected by the form chosen for both the speeches, and also, from the episode’s constant emphasis on Medea’s youth (Plantinga). She is bound to Medea by both kinship and supplication. However, by killing her brother, Medea had effectively severed the ties of kinship. Circe feels pity due to her position of

authority, but her response is ambiguous (Plantinga). She is also unable to extend any more hospitality towards Jason and Medea. Circe’s hospitality can also be vouched for with her instruction to Odysseus to seek out Tiresias and, later welcoming Penelope and Telemachus to her island.

In *Telegony*, Circe encourages her and Odysseus’ son, Telegonos, to seek out his father. Reaching Ithaca, he began to wreak havoc, and Odysseus coming to defend, was struck by a spear dipped in stingray poison. Penelope and Telemachus sail to Aeaea to bury him. It has been enjoined from various sources that Odysseus was not happy at Ithaca. He wanted to go back to the sea, and get involved in adventures, perhaps, that was the curse of a lifetime of dealing with the machinations of the Gods. In his poem *Ulysses*, Tennyson writes,

“For ever and forever when I move,
How dull it is to pause, to make an end,
To rust unburnish’d, not to shine in use!”

Later works derived from the *Odyssey* paint Odysseus as not entirely satisfied with his son. Telemachus is brave and clever, but he does not share his father’s gift of cunning and ruthlessness. In the epic, he tries to string his father’s great bow but fails thrice. He also punishes all the slave girls that laid with the suitors, with death, according to his father’s orders; but Telemachus in Miller’s book voices his guilt to Circe at having done so, “The girls would have had no choice. Odysseus would have known it.”

In Madeline Miller’s *Circe*, she does not want to let Telegonos go off the island that she had shielded with protective spells to protect her son from the Goddess Athena because of the prophecy that Telegonos would kill Odysseus. It is Circe who visits the ancient sea god Trygone to obtain the poison from his tail and give it to Telegonos to defend himself from the

world she had kept him away from. With Odysseus' death, Penelope decides to seek refuge in Aea, the only place Athena could not enter, because she knew that the Goddess would seek out her son. When she does appear, Telemachus refuses her offer to create a kingdom in the West. That offer is taken up by Telegonos, who had always wanted to leave the island. Circe is distraught by his decision but she lets her go, she cannot stop fate.

Circe was a single mother. Grant and Montrose have presented data that shows children with single mothers were at an increased risk of mortality and poor health as such women would have been shunned, and more likely to be affected by poverty and neglect. For women who had become pregnant out of wedlock, the fact that they had an illegitimate child was used as proof for accusing them as witches because of the widespread belief that witches had an excess of passion that made them commit "sexually deviant acts" (Findlay). Quoting from Grant and Montrose,

"Witch hunting targeted primarily single women... Women could also be branded as witches and killed as scapegoats for misfortune occurring in communities or for the "crime" of being sexually abused and made pregnant outside marriage."

Yubaba in *Spirited Away* has a giant baby named Bo. He wears a red cloth that has 'Bo' written on it. He also has super strength and threatens to break Chihiro's arm if she does not play with him. She is scared for the well-being of her baby, and like Circe, who confines Telegonos on an island, confines Bo to a giant room with giant toys to protect him from germs. The maternal aspect of Yubaba can also be traced to the tale of Kintaro and his mother. Kintoki, a brave warrior married a beautiful woman; but then he fell into a disgrace and died. His wife, fearing his enemies, flees to the mountains of Ashigara. A little boy was born to her and she named him Kintaro. The boy, having no one else to play with, befriended the animals in the mountainous forests and could smash rocks with his bare hands. They lived

in anonymity till Sadamitsu, a vassal of Lord Minamoto-no-Raiko, disguised as a woodcutter, discovered him and wanted to make him a Samurai. The mother’s heart was filled with joy as her greatest wish was for her son to become a Samurai before she died. She bade him farewell and continued to live on in the woods. Yubaba and Bo can be seen as the healthier versions of Nagasawa Rosetsu’s painting of Yamauba and Kintaro (Reider).

Yubaba’s hospitality can be inferred from her running the bathhouse itself. It is a place of *misogi* or ablutions, the practice of washing one’s entire body to purify oneself from misfortunes, sins, and pollution. She does not turn away the stink spirit but instead makes it Chihiro and Lin’s task to draw up his bath and clean him. It turns out that the stink spirit was a river god whose waters had been dangerously polluted. Yubaba appears helping and cheering Lin, Sen and the other workers on as they endeavour to get the pollutants out. When Noface turns into a demon, eating the employees, Yubaba shuts it in a room and implores it not to eat them.

Conclusion

Witch tales of old are being rewritten, and with research, context is being provided to the existence of the witch figure in several cultures across centuries. Circe, who had remained a minor figure in the epics, gained new interest with the publication of Madeline Miller’s novel. She was portrayed as a human, a Titaness, but with the human qualities of fallibility, envy, and love. Odysseus went from being a hero to a villain in his own tale. Reasons were given for her actions, and overlooked details in the existing epics were amplified – making the readers question why were the men on her island ever seen as innocent victims. Similarly, the appearance of Yubaba, and Studio Ghibli movies as a whole, prompted a new interest in Japanese mythology. There is no smoke without fire, and most myths are created to communicate incidents to future generations. Unrealistic expectations on women were the

reasons why the *yamauba* came into being, while the Western old created witches out of every woman who failed to conform to the socially accepted norms designated for them. Yubaba also has her fair share of funny moments, and with Chihiro calling her ‘Granny’ in the last scene, that is, perhaps, what she becomes. An old woman turned away from her house in keeping with the *Obasute yama* tradition; eccentric, temperamental and a businesswoman, not like women were supposed to be; yet she is still accepted by Chihiro – indicating a generation that is learning to love themselves, others, and one that disregards nonsensical social norms.

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